

The Tragic Consequences of Beauty and Love in William Shakespeare's *Romeo and Juliet*

Helen Kokei BASSEY (PhD)
0009-0004-1492-8974
DEPARTMENT OF ENGLISH
UNIVERSITY OF LAGOS,
AKOKA, LAGOS,
NIGERIA
kokispark@gmail.com

07030093797

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13336899>

Abstract

Human beings always want to possess beautiful things, which often lead to the objectification of women. However, just as men desire beautiful women and seek pleasure and gratification against all odds, women also break boundaries to fulfill their deep inner cravings for the men they love. This study investigates the themes of beauty and love and their tragic consequences in William Shakespeare's *Romeo and Juliet*. It focuses on the conflict between the enigmatic power of beauty and love and social expectations, as well as youthful vulnerability and folly. Deploying Sigmund Freud's Psychoanalytic concepts of the id and the unconscious, the study aims to argue and prove that although beauty and love have the capacity to transform, construct, promote and unite, they also possess the power to cause chaos, irrationality, destruction, and catastrophe. The study demonstrates that the love of Romeo and Juliet, despite being pure, inspirational, intensely passionate and reciprocal, becomes a catalyst for illogical and impulsive decisions and actions, inordinate desire, ambition, overwhelming influence, impetuosity and personal choices for pleasure and satisfaction that culminate in tragic consequences. The paper reveals that, even though Romeo and Juliet's friends, families, and their society each played a role in creating the tragic circumstances they find themselves in, it is ultimately their tragic flaws, impulsive decisions, actions and personal choices that propel their situation to its tragic end. The study recommends that true love should not be stifled by cultural norms and social conformity, and conflicts should be resolved swiftly, with forgiveness released easily.

Keywords: Beauty, Juliet, Love, Romeo, Tragic Consequences, William Shakespeare's *Romeo and Juliet*

Introduction

Emma Goldman expressively captures the life-changing and incalculable nature of love, thereby drawing attention to its resistance to exploitation and its exceptional power to inspire the human spirit. Thus, she says:

Love, the strongest and deepest element in all life, The harbinger of hope, of joy, of ecstasy; love the defier of all laws, of all conventions; love, the freest, the most powerful moulder of human destiny;... Man has bought brains, but all the millions in the world have failed to buy love. Man has subdued bodies, but all the power on earth has been unable to subdue love. Man has conquered whole nations, but all his armies could not conquer love. Man has chained and fettered the spirit, but he has been utterly helpless before love. High on a throne, with all the splendor and pomp his gold can command, man is yet poor and desolate if love passes him by. And if it stays, the poorest hovel is radiant with warmth, with life and colour. Thus, love has the magic power to make of a beggar a king. Yes, love is free, it can dwell in no other atmosphere (Emma Goldman 190).

The excerpt above is Goldman's observation on humans' inner cravings for beauty and love as well as their quest for satisfaction that leads to tragedy. Consequently, a critical eye on a woman's beauty and love gives a better understanding of why throughout the play, Romeo grapples with the conflict between his inordinate desires and the overwhelming influence of his love for Juliet. Romeo wants to possess beauty and in some ways, conquer it. Romeo is a tragic character whose qualities of destruction residing in his tragic nature, motivate his actions and personal choices as reflected in the play under study. For example, after falling in love with Juliet, Romeo becomes reckless, impatient, and resolute in his desire to possess her. In his quest and inordinate desire for Juliet's beauty, love and gratification, he endangers his life just to be close to her. Juliet, surprised to see Romeo asks, "How camest thou hither, tell me, and wherefore? /The orchard walls are high and hard to climb, /And the place of death, considering who thou art, / If any of my kinsmen find thee here" (2. 2. 64–67).

While responding to Juliet's question on how he gained access to her chambers, Romeo boldly declares:

With love's light wings did I o'erperch these walls; For stony limits cannot hold love out, And what love can do, that dares love attempt Therefore thy kinsmen are no stop to me... Alack, there lies more peril in thine eye Than twenty of their swords. Look thou but sweet, And I am proof against their enmity... My life were better ended by Their hate, Than death prorogued, wanting of thy love (2. 2. 68–80).

The excerpt above is a vivid reflection of blind passion that mutes the voice of reason and leads to the defeat and tragedy of Romeo and Juliet. They allow their emotions to gain sway over their reason and this leads to their bad decisions and personal choices. Their pursuit of beauty and love and their yearning for pleasure and the gratification of their hearts' desires is, perhaps, one

of the typical tragedies of life, a symbol for ever. Thus, a man, despite his genius, suffers also through his own excesses and tragic flaw, and bound to the stake of his own passionate sensibilities and consumed, as with fire. These lovers are impulsive in their pursuit of love and engage in defiant acts of rebellion just to satisfy their inner cravings for pleasure and gratification.

The overwhelming influence of their love manifests in the intense passion that springs up at first sight between Romeo and Juliet. In the play, love is a violent, ecstatic, overpowering force that supersedes all other values, loyalties and emotions. In the course of the play, the young lovers are driven by factors that are involved in tragic consequences to defy their entire social worlds like families. For instance, leaning out of her upstairs window, unaware that Romeo is below the orchard, Juliet asks why Romeo must be Romeo, why he must be a Montague, the son of her family's greatest enemy. Still unaware of Romeo's presence, she asks him to deny his family for her love (*Spark Notes LLC* 60). She adds, however, that if he will not, she will deny her family in order to be with him if he merely tells her that he loves her (2. 2. 33–36).

Essentially, the play also investigates the enigmatic power of beauty and love and its consequential tragedy. The Holy Bible categorically states that love is as strong as death, its jealousy as cruel as the grave, and that its flames are not just flames of fire but a most vehement flame (Song of Solomon Chapter 8 verse 6). It goes further to say that many waters cannot quench love, that even the floods cannot drown it, and that even if a man will give all the wealth of his house for love, it will be utterly despised (verse 7). This is seen playing out in the relationship between the central male and female characters in the literary text under study. This statement is very akin to one of Paulo Coelho's quotes that love is such an untamed force that when people try to control it, it destroys them. When they try to imprison it, it enslaves them. And when they try to understand it, it leaves them feeling lost and confused (74). This paves the way for us to understand and embrace the complex, often tumultuous nature of love as part of the warrior's journey.

According to Hebrew mythology and belief systems, King Solomon, the great and wisest king that ever lived says, "There are three things that amaze me, no, four things that I do not understand: how an eagle glides through the sky, how a snake slithers on a rock, how a ship navigates the ocean, HOW A MAN LOVES A WOMAN (The Holy Bible, Proverbs Chapter 30 verses 18 & 19-NLT). How a man loves a woman is indeed a great and painful mystery such that despite King Solomon's immense and unique wisdom, he could not understand the enigmatic power of beauty and love which draws men just like the lyre of Orpheus to a sudden sense of hope and then to their destruction, for which cause the woman is labelled a "femme fatale". It is indeed paradoxical and beyond human comprehension.

Literature Review

Human beings always want to possess beautiful things and this objectifies women. However, just as men desire beautiful women and yearn for pleasure and gratification against all odds, women also break boundaries to gratify their desperate inner cravings for the men they love. This is seen in the relationship between the male and female characters in the selected play. For instance, in *Romeo and Juliet*, though Juliet's beauty is described as frighteningly beautiful and irresistible, despite her loveliness, the tragedy will not have occurred if Romeo did not make the choice of bringing her into his life because of her alluring beauty. Anna Jameson notes that Shakespeare's women, being essentially women, either love or have loved, or are capable of loving; but Juliet is love itself.

To Jameson, the passion in Juliet's state of being, and out of it she has no existence. It is the soul within her soul; the pulse within her heart; the life–blood along her veins, “blending with every atom of her frame”. The love that is so chaste and dignified in Portia–so airy– delicate and fearless in Miranda, so sweetly confiding in Perdita–so playfully fond in Rosalind–so constant in Imogen–so devoted in Desdemona– so fervent in Helen– So tender in Viola–is each and all of these in Juliet. All these remind us of her; but she reminds us of nothing but her own sweet self (97). Ngugi wa Thiong'o asserts that the heart is hungry only for what it has chosen (23), and he who loves beauty does not complain while he is pursuing it (164). Daram and Ghoreishi are of the view that Romeo is bewitched by the charm of Juliet's beauty, for which cause he engages in various irrational actions to gratify his heart's desire for Juliet's beauty and love (83) which eventually leads to their tragedy.

However, Ayub Jajja argues that a Feminist reading of the play holds patriarchy and patriarchal values responsible for the tragic ending of *Romeo and Juliet* (233). According to Molly Mahood, recent critics have suggested that the love of Romeo and Juliet is the tragic passion that seeks its own destruction (192). To Glenn Wilson, when lovers see death as the ultimate consummation of love, the idea is that perfect love transcends mortal barriers and finds its proper dimension only in eternity (32). For Irving Ribner, as quoted by Taylor and Loughrey, *Romeo and Juliet* is a story of a hero and a heroine whose youthful vulnerability and folly is symbolic of the human condition (10).

The tragedy of Shakespeare characters under study, is a pointer to the fact that man often acts against his better judgment, and follows the call of his instincts and passion against the dictates of his reason, thereby “abandoning the dignity of his proper nature” and behaving like a beast (Mohammed Badawi 57). Wilson, while quoting Roberts P. notes that the tragedy of the characters under review, “provides warnings about the potentially dire consequences of human behaviour” (50).

Review of the concept of the Id and Unconscious

Jess Feist and Gregory Feist state that besides being unrealistic and pleasure seeking, the id is illogical and can simultaneously entertain incompatible ideas. All of its energy is spent for one purpose, to seek pleasure without regard for what is proper or just. Thus, the id is regarded as primitive, chaotic, inaccessible to consciousness, unchangeable, amoral, illogical, unorganised, and filled with energy received from basic drives and discharged for the satisfaction of the pleasure principle (34). Certainly, the id appears in that form in the major characters in the play under study. Ann Dobie corroborates Feist and Feist's assertion when she argues that, the id is also known to be the impetuous, unconscious part of the mind that has no understanding of any form of reality or consequence, for which cause it seeks for immediate gratification at all costs. This manifests in the language, actions, and choices of the major characters in the play. She further states that, as Freud describes it, the id strives “to bring about the satisfaction of the instinctual needs subject to the observance of the pleasure principle” (57).

Dobie's argument aligns with Yamin Liang's assertion that the id is primarily driven by the instinct for survival and is the source of all drives in the characters of the play. In fact, the id, representing man's selfish nature aimed at satisfying instincts at all costs, is evident in the major characters, who, are isolated from reality and immersed in their own perceptions, following the pleasure principle. Consequently, these characters exhibit behavioural difficulties such as impetuosity, hate, overwhelming love, rashness, passion, ambition, ignorance, rebellion, personal flaws, disobedience, naivety, and docility. These traits lead to their confusion, agony, and terrible

ordeals they endure. Furthermore, the id, which disregards consequences in favour of immediate gratification, manifests in the major characters' burning desires and choices, ultimately leading to their tragedy.

The Unconscious

Lois Tyson argues that the unconscious is the storehouse of those painful experiences and emotions, those wounds, fears, guilty desires, and unresolved conflicts we do not want to know about because we feel we will be overwhelmed by them (15). This argument is sustained by Dobie, who avers that for Freud, the unconscious is the repository for socially unacceptable ideas, wishes or desires, traumatic memories, and painful emotions put out of the mind through the process of psychological repression. He concludes that the unconscious plays a major role in what we do, feel, and say, although we are not aware of its presence or operations (55) as reflected in the major characters in the play. In fact, the unconscious, which has a very powerful and overwhelming influence on the characters' behaviour is made manifest even in their language use as pleasure and inordinate desire for beauty, love and satisfaction continues to disturb the clear lines of reason.

Moreover, as regards the unconscious processes, the human mind has often been recognised as a divided kingdom, and that the rational part is in contention with passion, imagination or even divine inspiration (Raman Selden 222). Selden goes further to say that reason has never had things all its own way because pleasure and desire continue to disrupt the clear lines of rationality (223) as vividly portrayed in the characters under review. Freud reaffirms Selden's assertion when he says that the conscious and unconscious decisions and actions of man invariably based on drives and forces reside in the human mind.

Essentially, it is the unconscious desires of the id for pleasure and satisfaction that motivate the desperate and violent cravings of the central male and female characters for gratification without an eye to consequences, and, of course, it precipitates their violent and tragic ends as vividly portrayed in the play. Interestingly, it has been observed that the concept of the unconscious has made psychoanalytic theory uniquely different from other theories in that it moves away from the rational and cognitive aspects of human behaviour to a study of the complexities of people's emotional lives and the motives which inform their actions, a mystery which this study intends to unravel.

Synopsis of *Romeo and Juliet*

Shakespeare's *Romeo and Juliet*, is known to be a tragic love story set in the city of Verona. The play is centred on two young passionate lovers from the Montagues and Capulets' feuding families. It is the most famous love story in the English literary tradition. The play focuses on romantic love, specifically the intense passion that springs up at first sight between Romeo and Juliet. In *Romeo and Juliet*, love is a violent, ecstatic, overpowering force that supersedes all other values, loyalties, and emotions. In the course of the play, the young lovers are driven to defy their entire social world: families; friends; and ruler. Love in *Romeo and Juliet* is a brutal, powerful emotion that captures individuals and catapults them against their world, and, at times, against themselves (*Spark Notes LLC* 15). Juliet's beauty enthralles Romeo so much that it kindles a deep and impetuous love that defies the enmity between their feuding families. To this end, they secretly get married a day after their meeting with the help of Friar Lawrence.

However, their happiness becomes short-lived and their hopes dashed when Romeo is banished from Verona for killing Juliet's cousin, Tybalt, who murders his friend, Mercutio. Lord Capulet and Lady Capulet, unaware of their daughter's secret marriage to Romeo, make arrangements for Juliet to marry County Paris. Juliet fakes her death as arranged by the Friar to

avoid marrying Paris. Unfortunately, Romeo returns to Verona when he hears of Juliet's supposed death. Being unaware of the plan and thinking Juliet truly dead, Romeo kills himself beside her. After Juliet awakes and finds Romeo dead, she also kills herself. Shakespeare's exploration of the enigmatic power of beauty and love in the play functions as the propelling force behind its tragic narrative, thereby exemplifying the complexities of human motives as well as the dichotomy of human experience. Interestingly, Shakespeare adeptly interlaced beauty and love in the play in order to reveal their transformative, constructive and destructive capabilities. Beauty appears to speak, call, and to beckon its admirers. In fact, it is known to create in men the inordinate desire and overwhelming influence for which it also seems to be the origin. Beauty as a quality, objectively and universally exists. Women must want to embody it and men must want to possess women who embody it (Naomi Wolf 12). Also, beauty makes use of women irrespective of their will or intent, and this buttresses the fact that beauty cannot be tamed even by those who possess it. For instance, Juliet's beauty is described as appealing, fascinating and enchanting. Its powerful and overwhelming effect on Romeo is such that he acts as if he has never known love before his encounter with Juliet. Interestingly, studies have also shown that beauty heightens the qualities of those who possess it.

By nature, men are attracted to what they see but they seem to have no power or ability to explain. After falling in love with Juliet, Romeo becomes reckless, impatient, and resolute in his desire to possess her. In his quest and inordinate desire for Juliet's beauty, love and gratification, he endangers his life just to be close to her. Juliet, surprised to see Romeo has this to asks, "How camest thou hither, tell me, and wherefore? /The orchard walls are high and hard to climb, /And the place of death, considering who thou art,/ If any of my kinsmen find thee here" (2. 2. 64–67). Indeed, beauty and love blind a man's senses with inordinate desire and a quest for pleasure and satisfaction against all odds as reflected in Romeo. Juliet's beauty enthralls Romeo so much that it kindles a deep and impetuous love that defies the enmity between their feuding families. To this end, they secretly get married a day after their meeting with the help of Friar Lawrence.

Romeo speaks about Juliet's surpassing beauty with so much passion, such that he imagines her to be the sun transforming the darkness into daylight (2. 2. 1–26). Similarly, Juliet is so overwhelmed by her love for Romeo that nothing else matters to her. She desires so much to be with Romeo that she longs for the night to fall earlier than expected (3. 2. 1–10). In her desperation to be with Romeo irrespective of the prevailing circumstances, Juliet cries, "Come, night; come, Romeo; come, thou day in night; /For thou wilt lie upon the wings of night whiter than New snow on a raven's back... Yet enjoyed. / So tedious is the day as is the night before/ Some festival to an impatient child that hath new robes/ And may not wear them..." (3. 2. 17–30). Juliet's love for Romeo is known to be heartfelt and wise. Romeo and Juliet's declaration of their deep love and devotion to each other is found in the balcony scene where they painfully and deeply regret the enmity of their families as well as the restrictions society places on them because of their names (2. 2. 38–49).

The balcony scene clearly reveals how the enmity between the Montagues and the Capulets makes it absolutely difficult for Romeo and Juliet to find the time or place to meet and let their passion grow; but the prospect of their love gives each of them the power and determination to evade the obstacles placed in their path (*Spark Notes LLC* 35). Juliet's dialogue with Romeo corroborates Feist and Feist's assertion that besides being unrealistic and pleasure seeking, the id is illogical and can simultaneously entertain incompatible ideas. All of its energy is spent for one purpose; to seek pleasure without regard for what is proper or just. Thus, the id, which is regarded as primitive, chaotic, inaccessible to consciousness, unchangeable, amoral,

illogical, unorganised, and filled with energy received from basic drives and discharged for the satisfaction of the pleasure principle (34) manifests in all the central characters' behaviour, actions and choices as vividly depicted in the selected plays.

To Juliet, words are not enough to convey the depth of her feelings for Romeo. Thus, she says, "...Worth: my true love is groan to such excess,/I cannot sum up sum of half my wealth" (2. 6. 30–34). The balcony scene is also where Romeo and Juliet passionately declare their profound and intense love for each other and determine to get married irrespective of the ancient feud between their families. In fact, the balcony scene is actually the point of decision about the course their lives will eventually follow. Consequently, the scene paves the way to their happy but brief marriage, their pain and grief, and even their untimely death. Romeo's tragic flaw, ambition and personal choice to marry Juliet against all odds makes him to throw caution to the wind for the love of a woman, and gives up his life to be with her in death. For Romeo, life is meaningless without Juliet (2. 2. 1–2, 45).

These lovers are impulsive in their pursuit of love and engage in defiant acts of rebellion just to satisfy their inner cravings for pleasure and gratification. In his pursuit of Juliet's beauty and love, Romeo becomes dauntless, forceful and relentless in his desire to possess her. In his quest for gratification, he puts his life on the line just to be close to Juliet. He also defies the banishment order all in a bid to have a glimpse of his love. And in the end, when he receives the news of Juliet's presumed death, he refuses to listen to anybody but quickly kills himself in order to spend eternity with Juliet (5. 1. 35–38). His inner cravings for Juliet's beauty and love cause him to go to extremes to prove the seriousness of his feelings. He secretly marries Juliet, the daughter of his father's worst enemy; he happily takes abuse from Tybalt and would rather die than live without his beloved (*Spark Notes LLC* 7).

Romeo's tragic flaw, ambition, ignorance, inordinate desires, rashness and his inability to think his actions through catapult him inevitably to his tragedy. He therefore becomes a major contributor to his tragedy. Most often, a man's heart desires a beautiful woman and yearns for satisfaction against all odds. Thus, in his quest for pleasure and inordinate desire for satisfaction at the hands of a beautiful woman, a man gets trapped in his own passions as vividly portrayed in the literary text under investigation. Essentially, the central male and female characters in the selected play are all motivated, even driven by inordinate desires, tragic flaws, ambition, fears, needs, overwhelming influence and conflicts of which they are unaware.

Romeo and Juliet also defy their friends. While Romeo abandons Mercutio and Benvolio after the feast in order to go to Juliet's garden, Juliet abandons her nurse and confidant and declares, "Ancient damnation! O most wicked fiend!/ Is it more sin to wish me thus forsworn.../ I'll to the friar to know his remedy./ If all else fail, myself have power to die" (3. 5. 235–242). Romeo also defies the ruler, Prince Escalus, when he returns to Verona just for the sake of Juliet after being banished by the Prince for killing Tybalt, Juliet's cousin. If Romeo is not too rash and emotional, so quick to fall into melancholy, the double suicide will not have occurred. If Juliet has deemed it fit to explain the truth to her parents, the double suicide might not have occurred too. But to wish someone were not as they were is to wish for the impossible. The love between Romeo and Juliet exists precisely because they are who they are. The destructive, suicidal nature of their love is just as much an aspect of their natures, as individuals and couple (*Spark Notes LLC* 55).

Also, the central male and female characters being examined are placed in certain circumstances, and it becomes obvious that, arising from the co-operation of their characters in these circumstances, certain actions take place. Unfortunately, their actions beget others which

also lead to many other actions until this series of inter-connected deeds lead by an apparently inevitable sequence to a catastrophe (Andrew Bradley 6). It is pertinent to note that, even though Romeo and Juliet's friends, families, and their society each played a role in creating the tragic circumstances they find themselves in, it is their tragic flaws, impetuous decisions, actions and personal choices that propel their difficult situation to its tragic end. In fact, the overwhelming influence of love in Romeo and Juliet is a brutal, powerful emotion that captures individuals and catapults them against their world, and, at times, against themselves. The play, therefore, portrays the chaos and passion of being in love, combining images of love, violence, death, religion, and family in an impressionistic rush leading to the play's tragic conclusion (*Spark Notes LLC* 16).

The id, which operates on the pleasure principle, and only takes into account what it wants while disregarding all consequences, is noticeable in the characters' inordinate desires, actions and personal choices for pleasure and gratification that lead to their catastrophic end. Essentially, it is the unconscious desires of the id for pleasure and satisfaction that motivate the desperate and violent cravings of the characters for gratification without an eye to consequences, and of course, it precipitates their violent and tragic ends as vividly portrayed in the selected play. The unconscious is therefore revealed as having a very powerful and overwhelming influence on the behaviour, actions and personal choices of the central characters in the plays under study. The id also reflects in Romeo's propensity for rash actions which get him and his beloved into a lot of trouble.

His impulsiveness proves his undoing. Love compels him to sneak into the garden of his enemy's daughter, risking death simply to catch a glimpse of her. Anger compels him to kill his wife's cousin in a reckless duel to avenge the death of his friend. Despair compels him to commit suicide when he hears about Juliet's presumed death. Such extreme behaviour dominates Romeo's character throughout the play and contributes to the ultimate tragedy that befalls the lovers. Had Romeo restrained himself from killing Tybalt, or waited even one day before killing himself after the news of Juliet's death, matters might have ended happily. Of course, though, had Romeo not had such depths of feeling, the love he shared with Juliet would never have existed in the first place (*Spark Notes LLC* 11–12).

Essentially, through his hasty actions, Romeo arguably drives the play toward tragedy more aggressively than any other character. Romeo never thinks his actions through, and his lack of foresight makes him responsible for their dire consequences (*Spark Notes LLC* 81). It therefore becomes obvious that the characters' irrational decisions and actions propel their situations to a tragic conclusion. But for their desperate inner cravings for pleasure and gratification, either Romeo or Juliet could have halted the headlong rush into destruction at any of the several points. The love of Romeo and Juliet is also immediate, violent and final. In fact, it has been discovered that in the voyage imagery of the play, they abandon themselves to a rudderless course that must end in shipwreck (5. 3. 117–120).

Studies have also shown that passion cannot be stifled, and when combined with the vigour of youth, it expresses itself through the most convenient outlet. Romeo and Juliet long to live for love or die for it. Consequently, the double suicide represents both the fulfillment of their love for each other and the self-destructive impulse that has surged and flexed beneath their love. Also, according to Taylor and Loughrey, G. W. F. Hegel, in considering the case of Romeo and Juliet has this to say: "The grounds on which these tender blossoms have been planted/ is alien to their nature; /we have no alternative left us but to lament /the pathetic transiency of such a beautiful love, which, /as some tender rose in the vale of this world of accident,/ is broken by

rude storms and tempests,... This pitiful state of our emotions is,/ however, simply a feeling of reconciliation that is painful, /a kind of unhappy blessedness in misfortune (38).

The tragedy of the characters under study, is a pointer to the fact that man often acts against his better judgment, and follows the call of his instincts and passion against the dictates of his reason, thereby “abandoning the dignity of his proper nature” and behaving like a beast (Mohammed Badawi 57). It is worthy of note that the central male and female characters in the play are epitomes of the human struggle in the face of the enigmatic power of beauty and love against the stifling and humiliating cultural norms and social conformity. The unconscious desires of the id for pleasure and immediate gratification manifest in the major characters’ tragic flaws, inordinate desires, ignorance, personal choices, overwhelming influence and impetuosity which, eventually drives them to the point of obsession and exhaustion, rendering them helpless and incapable of making logical decisions as vividly portrayed in the play.

Thus, the selected concepts are used to explore in detail the depths of the major characters’ motivation and conflicts and also tracing the intricate, mysterious operations of their minds. Also, the inner passion driving the major male and female characters under study, find expression in their personal choices and impetuous actions which, in turn, lead to their destruction. Moreover, when humans are overwhelmed by the desire for pleasure and gratification, they feel its pangs but they are unable to account for the harm it does to them. Consequently, men and women in pursuit of beauty and love become complex as they also become empty because emptiness is desire’s work. Men pursue in desire and also pursue women with words. Interestingly, words are regarded as the lover’s arrows which wound the heart through entering the ears, and then the wound becomes a form of enchantment. In fact, desire is revealed in the characters under study as a force which finds its only proof in the continued impossibility of wanting what it wants, and even wanting past the world’s limit of what can be had.

It therefore becomes apparent that, the Psychoanalytic concepts of the id and the unconscious, offer great insights into the major characters’ lives and the conflict of opposing forces within them; in fact, they dig up the unexcavated monuments of the characters’ minds. In other words, the interplay of these concepts, being the inner and outer forces which influence the complex behaviour and irrational decisions of these characters, provide great and fascinating insights into the complexity of people’s emotional lives and the motives which inform their actions and personal choices as reflected in the literary text. In fact, the tragedy of the major characters in pursuit of beauty/handsomeness and love is strange and terrible, and their actions defy rational understanding (Richard Gill 228) as vividly portrayed in the selected play.

The tragic flaws, ambition, ignorance, impetuosity and personal choices of tragic men attest to the fact that, a man with an overwhelming influence and inordinate desire for beauty and love is so lost to all sense of reality that he never asks himself what will be the consequences of his action. In fact, his action passes before him like the pictures that flash before the eyes of a drowning man, a triumphant scorn for the fetters of the flesh and when he eventually dies for the sake of a woman, exults in the power of love and man’s unconquerable mind (Bradley 161). The enigmatic power of love and beauty from which man cannot escape is relentless and immovable, and being doomed, man drifts struggling to destruction like a helpless creature borne on an irresistible flood towards a cataract (Bradley 19). Also, the strange fatality the central characters are unable to escape from and the vehement propensities that drive them to their doom attest to the blindness and helplessness of some men and some women in the face of their objects of

beauty and love, as well as their personal choices for pleasure and satisfaction, and, this, of course, is a painful mystery.

Conclusion

When humans are overwhelmed by the desire for pleasure and gratification, they feel its pangs but they are unable to account for the harm it does to them. Consequently, men and women in pursuit of beauty and love become complex as they also become empty because emptiness is desire's work. In fact, desire is revealed in the characters under study as a force which finds its only proof in the continued impossibility of wanting what it wants, and even wanting past the world's limit of what can be had. The central characters in the play are epitomes of the human struggle in the face of the enigmatic power of beauty and love against the humiliating cultural norms and social conformity.

Thus, the Psychoanalytic concepts of the id and unconscious have been used to explore in detail the depths of the major characters in the selected play and tracing the intricate, mysterious operations of their minds. Also, the inner passion driving the major characters under study, find expression in their choices and actions which in turn lead to their destruction. Consequently, the interplay of the Psychoanalytic concepts of the id and unconscious, being the inner forces which influence the complex behaviour and irrational decisions of these characters, have provided fascinating insights into the complexities of people's emotional lives and the motives which inform their actions and choices.

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